

KT4D

Knowledge Technologies
for Democracy

How should tech be regulated?

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Deliverable Abstract

This deliverable, first submitted in M12 as v1, provides a conceptual overview of some of the problems AI and big data pose to democracy from an institutional perspective. Module D focuses on the use of personal data and user profiling. Module E focuses on the control of individual speech and action. This version builds on v2 to begin to provide a toolkit to advance the state of the art in these two domains.

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3 Regulating the Use of Personal Data and User Profiling

Floridi (2018) offers a useful distinction between hard and soft ethics. “Hard ethics” encompasses the “values, rights, duties and responsibilities” discussed when formulating regulation (Floridi, 2018: 4). “Soft ethics” in contrast, discusses the same values, rights, duties, and responsibilities not from a regulation point of view, but from a post-compliance angle - i.e., what should be done once existing regulation has been obeyed (Floridi, 2018: 4). Whilst much of what has been discussed within this module so far may reasonably be seen as a form of soft ethics, it is important to understand the evolving sphere of hard ethics as related to AI and big data. In what follows, we outline some ways that have been considered in the literature as methods to regulate the technology space including structural regulation and transparent algorithms, the current concentration of power to AI companies, and existing and emerging regulation.

3.1 How Should Tech Firms Be Regulated?

Companies have significant influence over public discourse in online platforms, necessitating that the algorithms that shape these online platforms should be regulated and constrained to sufficiently consider the public interest (Susskind, 2018: 350).¹ Perhaps the easiest way of returning control of a public good to the people would be nationalisation of large AI companies and platforms. However, this also affords the government considerable power, to tailor public discourse to their interests (Susskind, 2018: 350). As such, nationalisation may lead to the aforementioned “digital gerrymandering” (Zittrain, 2014).

In lieu of these issues, some have suggested that companies be treated like public utilities and regulated in such a way as to protect the public interest (Cohen, 2016: 378 – 382; Rahman, 2018). In this way, many have argued in favour of ‘net neutrality’ – that companies for example cannot change the speed of internet connectivity, or limit access to content against their interests (Lanier, 2014). There are however some important differences between public utilities and technology companies. Utility companies are regulated because they control a public good (electricity etc), and whilst technology companies do this too, they uniquely have political power over who sees what.² As such, to compare them to utilities seems insufficient (Susskind, 2018: 157). Moreover, companies can be just as unjust and corrupt as governments, perhaps even more so, as such, why should we trust them to run these utilities over the government (Pasquale, 2017).

Moreover, since political power is associated with the ownership of online forums (and the algorithms that govern them), we might want to restrict how much of a forum (or how many forums) can be owned by one individual or company. In essence, by doing this we accept that some platforms will advantage some ideologies, but in allowing for no one company to monopolise this, we could adequately protect deliberation of all sorts (Susskind, 2018: 358). This form of structural regulation however may actually further stand to polarise political discourse online, with each platform becoming its own echo chamber.

¹ This is further discussed in section 3.2.

² This is explored in Module E.

If traditional regulation cannot provide all the answers then, the notion of transparent algorithms may be a useful element in a package of regulation. If all data usage and algorithms are clearly displayed in a manner which is understandable to the layman, we could greater trust these to govern our public platforms (Granka, 2010: 365; Manheim and Kaplan, 2019: 170; Susskind, 2018: 354). However, tech companies of course have private interests and may not be keen to display their information to their competitors. X (formerly Twitter) however have done this to a certain extent by open-sourcing their recommendation algorithm for example (Twitter, 2023a; Twitter 2023b). However, this move has been criticised due to mistakes, incomplete code, and underlying code being completely missing (Vaughan-Nichols, 2023). Open-source models will be further discussed in section 3.2.3.

One final notion to explore is the idea that technology itself can be democratised to mitigate some of the risks. Whilst it is possible to further limit the power of private firms to control deliberation, we could also incorporate democracy itself into technology (Susskind: 2018: 359). For example, we can imagine free platforms where anyone can modify code, or methods of scrutiny that could be applied to the creators of public forums before they are made available to the public.

3.2 Concentration of Power to AI Companies

One of the major challenges of governing artificial intelligence (AI) is the concentration of power to AI companies that develop and deploy AI systems. This is especially so when privately developed AI systems are integrated into public societal infrastructure, such as health, education, transportation, and communication. This integration threatens to give these actors disproportionate influence over the public arena, where society communicates and forms opinions (Jungherr & Schroeder 2023). Moreover, such amalgamation limits the public scrutiny and democratic participation in the development and use of AI systems, as they become less visible and assessable (Maham & Küspert 2023).

Some scholars have argued that a greater antimonopoly approach to governance is needed to prevent the AI oligopoly from abusing its power and harming the economic, social, and political interests of the public (Ganesh & Narechania 2023). An anti monopoly approach would entail using various tools, such as industrial policy, network and platform regulation, public options, and cooperative governance, to shape the market structure and facilitate competition and innovation in the AI sector.

AI can also undermine democracy through concentration of power to actors which lack democratic accountability. These structural and systemic risks especially relate to the economic incentives that shape how organisations develop and utilise AI systems, in contrast to the more direct risks outlined in 2.4.2.

3.2.1 Structural and Systemic Risks to Democratic Participation

Structural risks concern how the AI systems interact with larger social, political, and economic forces. This includes whose voice is heard and who holds the power in society. Moreover, AI influences the quality and diversity of information that citizens receive through algorithms that filter, rank,

recommend, or generate content. This can create distrust and polarisation that undermines democratic deliberation and public opinion formation. These systemic risks include:

- Centralisation of power to few private companies given the prohibitive compute, training and data requirements of AI models versus states.
- Lack of democratic oversight and alignment of AI with the popular will, especially with the geopolitical and national securitisation of AI.
- Diminishing epistemic agency of citizens essential to democratic public sphere and representation due to reliance on AI.
- Rise of inequality through AI's impacts on labour market and economy, displacement and exploitation of workers.
- Societal and political distrust if personalised AI systems violate rights and liberties of citizens as part of public services.

3.2.2 The Question of Open-Source AI Models

Open-source models are closely related to the debate about AI-driven centralisation of power. Open-source software is based on freely shared source code and data that allows anyone to modify, deploy and use the system, although there is debate as to what degree this definition is applicable to AI. On the one hand, open-source AI models can foster openness, pluralism and lessen centralization of power, which are essential pillars of democracies.³ On the other hand, such models can also create security risks, such as the proliferation of disinformation and deepfakes, that can undermine the quality and integrity of democratic deliberation and decision-making (Hintersdorf et al. 2023). Therefore, some scholars and policymakers have argued that access to advanced open-source AI models should be limited or regulated, for instance by imposing licensing requirements on AI developers and users (Seger et al. 2023). However, this approach may entail a trade-off between security and openness, as it could result in the concentration of power and influence to a few AI labs or companies, which are not accountable or transparent to the public. Moreover, it could stifle innovation and diversity in the AI field, and create barriers for smaller or marginalised actors to participate and benefit from AI applications.

Some also argue that open-source development in the context of AI does not carry the usual benefits of democratisation given the massive computational resources required to build and deploy AI at scale, and accordingly the term has become co-opted by large technology companies such as OpenAI or Meta (Widder, West & Whittaker 2023). In any case, the regulation of frontier AI models in the interest of safety can still violate principles of open societies and serve to concentrate power on AI companies. Thus, the question of how to balance the security and openness of AI models in democratic societies is a complex and urgent one, that requires careful consideration of the potential impacts and implications of more open or closed model releases going forward. Such discussions have already

³ The features and pillars of democracy are discussed in Section 1.3 of this Module.

started to take shape, and were particularly fierce during the final stages of the AI Act trilogues (Council of the EU, 2023).

Recognizing the innovation potential of open-source, the AI Act (see Recitals 102-104; Articles 2, 53, 54) does not apply to AI systems that are released under open-source licences, unless they are monetised or placed on the market as high-risk AI systems or prohibited systems under Article 5. Open-source in this context is understood as models (including their parameters, architecture and weights) that can be openly run, shared, accessed, used, copied, modified and redistributed under relevant licences. Such AI models are also exempt from most of the transparency-related requirements set for general-purpose AI models. However, these exemptions do not cover openly released general-purpose AI models that present systemic risks, based on their high impact capabilities (e.g. trained on more than 10^{25} FLOPs of computing power).

3.2.3 Competition perspective

The way the European Union has traditionally approached and mitigated the concentration of power is through competition law and functioning of the single market. The EU's legislative framework has sought to prevent the formation of monopolies, curb anti-competitive practices, and dismantle barriers to cross-border trade between the member states. The overarching policy goal has been to ensure a dynamic, competitive market environment that fosters innovation, lowers prices, and enhances consumer choice. This approach is also reflected in the AI Act, which predominantly focuses on safety of AI products placed on the EU market under the new legislative framework (NLF). Some have also argued that the EU's risk-based approach to AI regulation is an epistemic signalling tool to advance a globally competitive common European AI market (Paul, 2023).

However, as digital platforms and AI technologies increasingly dominate the market, traditional competition law frameworks face challenges in effectively addressing the unique dynamics of the digital economy. These platforms often benefit from network effects, data accumulation, and vertical integration, which can entrench their market positions and stifle competition. Consequently, there is growing recognition within the European Union that additional regulatory measures may be necessary to ensure a level playing field and to prevent the abuse of market power. This has led to initiatives such as the Digital Markets Act (DMA), which aims to complement existing competition law by imposing specific obligations and restrictions on gatekeeper platforms to preserve fair competition and protect consumers.

The application of competition law is further complicated by the geopolitical landscape in which Europe operates, particularly in light of the growing trend toward AI nationalism (Kak, 2024). This has spurred calls for the European Union to significantly increase its investment in digital public infrastructure, including high-performance computing, shared datasets, and open-source AI development. These initiatives are part of a broader AI industrial policy (e.g. European Chips Act, Strategic Technologies for Europe Platform) aimed at reducing reliance on foreign technology and asserting the EU's competitiveness in an AI industry currently dominated by a few major US corporations. The strategic focus on developing European capabilities is seen as essential not only for economic competitiveness but also for safeguarding digital sovereignty and ensuring European values, such as privacy.

3.3 Current Regulatory Frameworks

3.3.1 Existing and Emerging Policies

The EU's evolving digital and AI policy has been through at least three development phases. The gradual progress has moved towards more robust legislation through the 1) initial era of ethics principles and guidelines (2017-2019); 2) preliminary policy and governance on more specific domains, e.g. NIST framework (2020-2022); to reach 3) actual policies and legislation (2023-2024). An important culmination point of this was the set of AI agreements and declarations in November and December 2023, including the agreement on AI Act, the US Executive Order, the G7 Hiroshima agreement, and the Bletchley Declaration. Importantly, this has meant a shift in discourse to safety and security of general-purpose AI (GPAI) systems. As is seen in the former discursive shifts towards securitisation, this shift includes a risk of narrowing down the problem to the perspective of security and may result in overlooking broader angles such as AI ethics and democracy. This is important not only from the perspective of the drafting and scope of future policy and legislation, but also because the next challenge will be the actual implementation and enforcement of this regulation.

AI policy is emerging and evolving simultaneously at different governance levels. The multilateral global governance initiatives include Recommendation on the Ethics of Artificial Intelligence published by UNESCO (2022), AI principles by OECD (2019), The Global Partnership for Artificial Intelligence (GPAI, 2021) building on the OECD recommendations on AI. Furthermore, collaboration has emerged also among the G7 Hiroshima AI process Comprehensive Policy Framework (European Commission, 2023a) and in the context of EU and US bilateral cooperation. The supra-national level legislation from the EU, such as the AI Act, Digital Service Act and the Digital Markets Act, are applied at the national level. Other national level initiatives include the US Executive Order published in October 2023, and the UK pro-innovation approach to AI. Also China, India and Latin America have taken stances in recognising the societal and political implications of AI in their own ways. In China, the government has published a Position Paper of the People's Republic of China on Strengthening Ethical Governance of Artificial Intelligence (AI) (Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the People's Republic of China, 2022). India on the other hand has adopted an intensely growth and innovation oriented approach without developing a robust AI regulation (NITI Aayog, 2018). Most recently, the Economic Commission for Latin America and the Caribbean (ECLAC) launched The first Latin American AI Index, which forms a stepping stone towards further adoption and collaboration on AI in the region (ECLAC, 2023).

In addition to governments and international organisations, also the industry level has pushed their own initiatives. These include Partnership on AI (2024), the EU driven AI Pact (European Commission, 2023b) and the voluntary AI commitments in the US (The White House, 2023b). Still, among the manifold openings in the field, the EU has managed to position itself as the regulatory leader on digital and AI policies, hoping to leverage the so-called Brussels effect (Bradford 2020), although now faces catch-up by other countries. The AI Act is based on a new legislative framework, digital markets and product legislation unlike fundamental rights-oriented GDPR. While the risk-based approach of the AI Act is future-oriented, it also comes with policy baggage, such as technocratic tendencies (Kaminski 2023) and often underestimates the cultural and societal impact of such technologies (Ahern, et al., 2024).

Some of the relevant questions for the future of European AI regulation include:

- To what extent is the use case product legislation and risk-based approach enshrined in the AI Act fit for general-purpose AI systems?
- Should there be restrictions on the development of increasingly larger models? Are quantitative thresholds such as 10^{25} FLOPs of compute power the right tool?
- How can we balance technical expertise with effective democratic control in AI regulation; e.g. civil society perspective in standard-setting?
- What should be the role of citizen participation and NGOs in AI governance?
- Can regulation that focuses on individual rights uphold and safeguard collective democratic principles and communicative norms?
- To what extent is the proposed regulation and its enforcement enough (e.g. GDPR vs use of copyrighted data in LLMs) or are new institutions needed?

The current EU approach to AI regulation faces several challenges and limitations that need to be addressed. One of the main issues is to what degree product legislation approach is fit for mitigating more systematic and democratic risks of AI systems and the lack of resources for regulatory and enforcement agencies. Another challenge is the compatibility of the EU approach with the collective bargaining and co-determination models that are prevalent in some member states. How can the EU ensure that workers are adequately involved in the governance of AI systems that affect their work environment and conditions? A third issue is the power relations and liability between the providers and the users of general-purpose AI systems. The EU approach seems to be unclear or reluctant to assign liability to the providers of AI systems, which may create an imbalance of power and responsibility between them and the users or deployers of the systems. Finally, the sustainability and material footprints of AI systems are arguably overlooked in the EU approach, despite it being a potentially important leverage point.

3.3.2 Underlying Democratic Implications of Policy and Regulatory Approaches

The regulation of AI is a complex and contested issue that involves multiple actors, interests, and values. The policy and regulatory approaches to AI have underlying democratic implications that need to be critically examined. Smuha (2021) argues that the global landscape of AI regulation has shifted from a 'Race to AI' to a 'Race to AI Regulation', as different actors and regions compete to set the norms and standards for AI development and deployment. However, the drivers and motivations behind AI regulation are not homogeneous or neutral, but rather reflect the interests and values of different stakeholders from a critical political economy perspective (Paul, 2023). First, AI regulation can be seen as a normative project of applied ethics, aiming to ensure that AI is aligned with human dignity and rights. Second, it can also be seen as a technocratic rational choice endeavour, balancing between the promotion of innovation and the mitigation of ethical risks. Thirdly, AI regulation can be influenced by regulatory capture by industry, which may seek to shape the rules in their favour or avoid strict oversight. Finally, AI regulation can be driven by the state competition perspective, which views AI as a strategic asset and a source of geopolitical power.

One way to AI regulation is to examine the imaginaries and narratives that shape the public and policy discourse on it. Bareis and Katzenbach (2022) argue that national AI strategies are a form of co-shaping AI development and deployment, as they offer imaginaries, allocate resources, and set rules. However, they also show that the imaginaries and narratives of AI regulation differ significantly across countries, reflecting their cultural, political, and economic contexts. Another way to approach this issue is to explore the different meanings and goals of democratising AI, which is often invoked as a desirable aim. Seger, Ovadya, Siddarth et al. (2023) identify four kinds of AI democratisation that are commonly discussed: the democratisation of AI use, development, profits, and governance. They also discuss the methods and challenges of achieving each form of democratisation, and highlight the need for the democratisation of AI governance as a way to navigate trade-offs and risks.

A final, critical approach to the values behind AI governance is to analyse the convergence and divergence of AI ethics principles and guidelines, which are meant to provide normative guidance for AI design and use. Corrêa et al. (2023) find that there is a substantial convergence of AI ethics principles and guidelines across the world, but also note that democratic values are interpreted differently depending on the context and perspective. They suggest that AI ethics principles and guidelines should be complemented by more concrete and contextualised mechanisms and practices. Similarly, Jobin, Ienca and Vayena (2019) and Hagendorff (2020) provide comprehensive evaluations of AI ethics principles and guidelines, and point out the gaps and limitations of these documents. They call for more clarity, consistency, and operationalization of AI ethics principles and guidelines, as well as more stakeholder involvement and accountability.

3.3.3 Effective Democratic Control in AI Regulation

One of the main challenges for democratic AI governance is the capacity to implement and enforce the regulation, which requires adequate resources, expertise, and coordination among the relevant authorities. On 29 May 2024, the European Commission unveiled the AI Office to oversee and support the implementation and application of the AI Act, especially in relation to general-purpose AI models (European Commission, 2024). To facilitate well-informed decision-making, the AI Office will engage with Member States and the broader expert community through specialised forums and expert groups. At the EU level, the AI Office will closely collaborate with the European Artificial Intelligence Board, which includes representatives from Member States (European Commission, 2024b). However, the AI Office may face difficulties in ensuring compliance and accountability of AI providers and deployers, especially in the case of high-risk AI systems that pose serious threats to public goods. Another challenge is the standard setting process, which is crucial for defining the technical requirements and specifications for high-risk AI systems. Under the AI Act, creation of standards is delegated to European Standard Organizations (e.g. CEN-CENELEC), which are dominated by the AI industry and lack civil society representation (Ada Lovelace Institute 2023). The power of standard-setting bodies in implementation of the AI Act may therefore undermine the democratic legitimacy of the regulation.

One opportunity is to promote deliberative processes and mini-publics in AI governance, which refer to the involvement of randomly selected yet representative samples of citizens in decision-making, under expert facilitation. Deliberative democracy and mini-publics can enhance the quality and legitimacy of AI governance, by fostering legitimacy and public acceptance as well as by providing

critical and constructive feedback to the AI industry and policymakers (Buhmann & Fieseler 2021; 2023). However, deliberative democracy and mini-publics also face practical and theoretical obstacles, such as the complexity and opacity of AI systems, the power asymmetries and knowledge gaps between experts and citizens, and the potential manipulation and co-optation of the deliberative processes by vested interests.

To align with the EU's digital and green transition agenda, one of the potential governance responses is to promote sustainable AI that can foster smaller and more transparent models that respect democratic values. This could be achieved by drawing lessons from the regulation of life sciences and medical industry, such as involving diverse stakeholders in the decision-making process. Moreover, more participatory approaches to AI governance and standard setting are needed overall, such as support for NGOs and CSOs to engage in AI policy. As a positive example, on 30 July 2024, the European AI Office announced a call for expressions of interest to contribute to the development of the first general-purpose AI Code of Practice. They invited eligible general-purpose AI model providers, downstream providers, industry organisations, civil society organisations, rights holders, academia, and other independent experts to express their interest in participating in the multistakeholder initiative (European Commission, 2024).

3.3.4 Profiling and Targeting under the EU Legal Framework

Profiling as defined in Article 4(4) of the GDPR is any form of automated processing of personal data which consists of the use of personal data to evaluate certain personal aspects relating to a natural person, and in particular, to analyse or predict aspects which concern their performance at work, economic situation, health, interests, personal preferences, reliability, behaviour, location or movements. Profiling is a common data processing activity which may adversely affect the rights and freedoms of data subjects and may also be used for political purposes.⁴

Profiling may pose a challenge in democracy due to the fact that the decision-making process creates unbalanced distribution among citizens on one side and government and organisations and companies on the other side. Essentially, decisions based on automated profiling techniques may not allow the citizens to challenge the reasoning behind the process and this may have a negative impact on effective participation in a democracy (Ferraris, Valeria, et al, 2013).

The French Data Protection Authority defines targeted advertising as a technique that aims to identify people in order to deliver specific advertising messages to them based on their individual characteristics (French Data Protection Authority (CNIL), n.p.). Government and entity practices that are incentivized by target advertising models may endanger human rights indirectly or contribute to the violation of rights of a group of people. The risks caused are based on an initial violation of privacy of individuals or citizens that occurs in the targeted advertising service (Ranking Digital Rights, 2019:2a). For example, targeted political advertising for citizens may hinder the citizens freedom of expression and information by denying the citizens the right to freely elect and choose their representatives Ranking Digital Rights, 2019:2b.⁵

⁴ For more on profiling see section 2 in Module D.

⁵ For more on political targeted advertising see module D.

3.3.4.1 Profiling and Targeted Advertising

As discussed in section 2, targeted advertising uses data about individuals to select and display advertisements or other forms of commercial content and personal data is obtained either directly or indirectly from the data subjects. The personal data that has been collected are processed for the purpose of user profiling, deriving analytics, machine learning, and cognitive computing technologies (Regulating targeted and behavioural advertising in digital services, 2021). Individuals can thus be grouped according to their interests, attitudes and behaviour. This section outlines the ways that legal frameworks and regulation concerning profiling and targeted advertising intersect with individuals' freedoms.

Article 8(2) of the Charter outlines consent as a legal basis for the processing of personal data. Similarly, as outlined above, the GDPR outlines the conditions of consent to be a freely given, specific, informed, and unambiguous indication of data subjects' wishes, given through a statement or a clear affirmative action. The ePrivacy Directive also requires users' consent for placing of cookies and other tracking devices on their terminal.

On the one hand, the Digital Markets Act (DMA) that aims to ensure that gatekeepers act fairly online provides that gatekeeper platforms may no longer track end users outside of the gatekeepers' core platform service for the purpose of targeted advertising, without effective consent having been granted (Article 5(2) DMA). It also places an obligation for periodical auditing of gatekeepers' profiling techniques to ensure transparency. On the other hand, the Digital Services Act (DSA) requires platforms to be transparent in their content moderation and lays down rules on transparency of content moderation. The European Commission affirmed that the DSA protects freedom of expression, including freedom and pluralism of the media (European Commission, 2023a). The legislation strikes a balance between combating illegal content and safeguarding freedom of expression and information online. This also relates to the protection from government interference in people's freedom of expression and information (European Commission, 2023b).

The EDPB Guidelines on the targeting of social media users states that, there are two legal bases which could theoretically justify the processing that supports the targeting of social media users i.e., data subject's consent or legitimate interest. The EDPB noted that in cases where a data controller seeks to rely on legitimate interest, the duties of transparency and the right to object need to be carefully considered. Furthermore, data subjects should be given the opportunity to object to the processing of their data for targeted purposes before the processing is initiated (EDPB Guidelines 8/2020 on the targeting of social media users, 2020).

There is a huge risk for discrimination when it comes to targeted advertising for example, job offers can directly exclude individuals from material opportunities. On the flip side, it can also facilitate deliberate inclusion targeting vulnerable groups with products such as gambling and payday loans (Griffin, 2022).

3.3.4.1.1 Political Advertising

In 2020, as part of the European Democracy Plan, the European Commission announced an initiative to complement the DSA's rules on online advertising by way of a proposal concerning sponsored political advertising (COM(2021) 731 final) (European Parliament, 2023a). The proposal was presented at the end of 2021 and specifically aims to foster more transparency in this area. The European Parliament and European Council adopted the new regulation in early 2024 (Regulation (EU) 2024/900). It came into force on 9 April 2024, with most provisions set to take effect on 10 October 2025. However, the provisions preventing discrimination by providers of political advertising services based on the place of residence or establishment of the advertising European political party or sponsor took effect immediately, ensuring they are in place for the 2024 European elections (Think Tank: European Parliament; 2024). Regulation (EU) 2024/900 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 March 2024 on the transparency and targeting of political advertising aims to establish clear and harmonised rules to provide transparency in political advertising.

Wojciech Wiewiórowski, the European Data Protection Supervisor, has underlined that "Political communication is essential for citizens, political parties and candidates in order to fully participate in democratic life. To preserve our democracy, we also need strong rules to combat disinformation, voter manipulation and interference with our elections. We need to do more if we want to tackle the many risks surrounding the use of targeting and amplification techniques for political purposes" (EDPS, 2022). In order to serve political advertisements to individuals, both data provided directly by individuals and data which is acquired from their online activities are used (European Parliament, 2023b). The political advertisement targeting process "has been observed to have specific negative effects on citizens' rights including their freedoms of opinion and of information, to make political decisions and exercise their voting rights" (European Parliament, 2023c).

Political advertising indeed has a significant potential to influence democratic processes. In order to protect democracy, the EDPS has called for more restrictions to be put on the categories of data which may be used for political advertising purposes; specifically, the use of sensitive personal data will be banned (European Parliament, 2023d). The EDPS' Opinion 2/2022 which critiques the Proposed Regulation, appreciates the essential nature of political communication for democracy and stresses the interdependency between the right to privacy established in Article 7 of the Charter and the right to data protection under Article 8 of the Charter (EDPS, 2022:2a). At the same time, the Opinion recalls the numerous risks which are posed by such activities and calls for a "full ban of microtargeting for political purposes" and the introduction of "further restrictions on the categories of data that may be processed for the purposes of political advertising, including targeting and amplification, in particular prohibiting targeted advertising based on pervasive tracking" (EDPS, 2022:2b).

The proposed Regulation complements the GDPR and the DSA, but goes further than the DSA in "expand(ing) the categories of information to be disclosed in the context of political advertising as well as the scope of the relevant service providers concerned" (EDPS, 2022:5a). Thus, while the DSA provides for transparency requirements for online platforms, the proposed Regulation "seeks to cover the entire spectrum of political advertising publishes" (EDPS, 2022:5a).

Microtargeting has been used to adversely affect democratic processes in the past. For instance, during the 2016 US elections, it was discovered that "Russian operatives" utilised Facebook to specifically target Black Americans with the aim of dissuading them from voting (New York Times,

2023a). Similarly, Donald Trump’s political campaign made significant use of targeting to rally voters, serving them with “inflammatory messages” (New York Times, 2023b). More recently in Europe, Orbán “campaign sent tailored advertisements to people they already had data on, as well as sending targeted advertisements according to gender, in which advertisements discussing the war in Ukraine were sent only to male Facebook users” (EDRi, 2023).

As pointed out by EDRi, politicians make use of special category data, such as ethnicity, religion, health information, and sexual orientation “to target different parts of the population with different messages. If they say different things to different voters, it allows them to spread misinformation to fire up their supporters and deter people from going to the polls” (EDRi, 2023b). On 6 November 2023 a political agreement was reached on the proposed Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on the transparency and targeting of political advertising (European Parliament Legislative Train Schedule, 2023a). According to the European Parliament’s Legislative Train, the law will prohibit profiling with special categories of personal data, restrict non-EU entities financing political ads within the EU, and establish a dedicated database to examine political advertisements (European Parliament Legislative Train Schedule, 2023b). It is highly necessary that the Regulation is urgently adopted so as to protect EU democratic processes.

3.3.4.1.2 Challenges and Opportunities

Profiling and targeted advertising may create challenges and opportunities for fostering democracy. For example, microtargeting has allowed advertisers to discriminate in a manner that is difficult for regulators to catch (New York Times, 2023a). Using language that suggests that job offers, housing or credit opportunities are being offered to people of certain race, gender, age or other protected categories is illegal (New York Times, 2023b). A new study showed that targeted advertisements shown to a set of participants were pitching more expensive products from lower-quality vendors than similar products that showed up during a simple web-search (New York Times, 2023c). Advertisers can thus easily hide their preferences in targeted advertising through the algorithm and this has been demonstrated repeatedly by Facebook which has enabled discriminatory advertisement (Faife, et al., 2021).

Targeted advertising evidently poses a threat to democracy and this may be demonstrated in the verified instance of Russian interference in the 2016 United States presidential elections. The Democratic National Committee and its cyber response team made a public announcement that Russian hackers had compromised its computer network (Federal Bureau of Investigation, n.p.). Additional pertinent instances within the EU include the political advertising that is widely used by the Chinese platform, TikTok (China Observers in Central and Eastern Europe, 2023). This may pose a threat to democracy through manipulation campaigns.

3.3.5 Legislation on Automated Decision Making

Article 22 of the GDPR gives individuals the right not to be subject to decisions made solely based on automated processing, including profiling, if these decisions have legal effects or similarly significant effects against an individual. However, there are limitations to this right e.g., when the decision is

necessary for the performance of a contract, authorised by law, or based on explicit consent. In such cases, measures must be in place to protect the individual's rights and interests, including the right to human intervention, to express their viewpoint, and to contest the decision.

Automated Decision Making (ADM) systems enable governments and organisations to enhance efficiency e.g., by automating routine tasks however, the systems may aggravate discrimination against marginalised groups by relying on data that reflects pre-existing real-world inequities, undermining vital democratic and human rights protections (Maya Recanati, 2024). Although these systems offer advantages such as improved efficiency, accuracy, and decision-making consistency, they also present considerable challenges to democratic values and institutions.

ADM, particularly through AI, can have significant implications for freedom of speech. On the one hand, moderating content on social media platforms can help remove harmful content. On the other hand, it can also lead to over-censorship, where legitimate expressions are mistakenly flagged and removed and thereby limiting the freedom of speech of individuals (Eve Gaumont, Catherine Régis; 2023).

Similarly, ADM systems might be employed for surveillance, which could suppress free speech. Individuals may choose to self-censor if they suspect their communications are under observation (Julius Haas; 2020). ADM systems may pose a limitation on journalism. More specifically, automated systems can affect journalism by prioritising certain types of content over others, potentially influencing public discourse by reducing the variety of perspectives accessible to the audience (Article 19; 2018). This can shape opinions, beliefs, and attitudes on various issues, ultimately impacting public opinion and decision-making.

The use of ADM systems can bypass traditional, transparent democratic processes. This will result in reduced opportunities for public debate and citizen participation (Nardine Alnemi; 2023). This is due to the fact that the black box nature of ADM systems, as explained in Section 2.3.2, may make it difficult for the public to understand and challenge how decisions are made. Moreover, when ADM systems are used to make decisions, it may be challenging to hold any individual or institution accountable for the outcomes. This can undermine trust and confidence in democratic institutions and authorities. For these reasons, balancing the benefits of ADM with the need to protect freedom of speech is crucial.

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